

Big Data Analytics and Banks

Ravindra Bavaskar¹, Kalyani Sahastrabuddhe² and Antra Rastogi³

¹Assistant Professor, ²Assistant Professor and ³Student,
Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India

Abstract:

Big data analytics is soon becoming a mainstay in the present banking sector. Banks are a perpetual mine of raw data, which they can use to source acumens into consumer' behavior. Especially regarding account transactions, enhancing consumer understanding of the banking system to attract and retain consumers, and augmenting trade performance. The results of this review have revealed that most banks use big data analytics for Fraud Detection and Credit risk analysis. However, the cost of implementation, poor data quality, lack of trained staff, and skeptical banking executives still pose challenges for its uptake in the banking zone. This review has also mentioned the kinds of technologies like BlockChain and Data Mining and their uses in enhancing the whole banking experience in terms of faster transactions at a reduced cost and improvement on customer satisfaction.

Keywords: Big Data, Data Analytics, Banking

Introduction

Banks are a perpetual mine of raw data, which they can use to source acumens into consumer' behavior. Especially regarding account transactions, enhancing consumer understanding of the banking system to attract and retain consumers, and augmenting trade performance (Hoppermann and Bennett, 2014). Big data analytics can help develop risk models to notice and predict fraud warning signs, non-payment and consumer departure, etc., using data mining and artificial intelligence.

The banks use big data analytics for asset management, market analysis, online/ off-line transactions, which are flowing data, i.e., banking data is characterized by its huge volume and velocity of changes it undergoes unceasingly (Davenport and Harris, 2007). It has different dimensions such as technical, analytic, strategic, etc. (Laney, 2001; Gualtieri, 2012; Howie, 2013; Wamba et al., 2015). The 2008 financial crisis faced by the

banking sector has forced the banks to turn toward technology such as Big Data Analytics, IoT (Internet of Things), BlockChain to improve the banks' constancy and value of its services (Das et al., 2018)

Even though big data analytics has proven uses in the banking sector, some institutions are still unclear about its capacity to generate value, or some banks are unable to scale up for increasing their overall profits or cost reduction, etc. this may be related to the fact that the value generation depends upon the strategic goals of the organizations (Cavanillas et al. 2016; Ghoshal et al., 2014). Thus this review plans to study the various nuances of big data analytics in the banking sector.

Literature Review

According to Bhattacharya et al. (2011), the two most important criteria in adopting Big Data Analytics are "Fraud Detection" and "Credit Risk Analysis" (See Table 1).

Table 1: Banking and Big Data Analysis

Author	Big Data Analytics
Bhattacharya et al., 2011	"Fraud Detection" and "Credit Risk Analysis"
Comoros et al., 2014	Analyzing consumer behavior via unstructured data collected from their online social media activity
Manyika et al., 2011	Micro-segmentation of consumers to better mark them for specific advertisements and sales campaigns
He et al., 2016	Good relations with consumers not only enhances satisfaction but also helps to retain customers
Liu, 2012	Sentiment analyses- how people feel about the brands, products, services, events, organizations
Ghoshal et al. 2014	Operational Analytics- Different and new data sources and techniques lead to better efficiency in the current processes
Woerner and Wixom, 2015	Helps to revolutionize business models to create a unique value to consumers via exclusive products and services
Bedeley and Iyer, 2014	Better <i>Competitive advantage</i>
Srivastava and Gopalkrishnan, 2015	<i>Transactional analysis</i> - to assess the consumers' pattern of spending to identify probable consumers for selling customized financial products <i>Sentimental Analysis</i> – to apprehend the consumers' sentiments and assess how it impacts the functioning of the bank

Nevertheless, on the other hand, the various data-related challenges range from low data quality, privacy & security, data incompatibility in processing data for specific purposes (Coumaros et al., 2014). The other trials regarding big data analysis are lack of properly trained staff; top executives are at times not in favor, high implementation costs, etc. (Kshetri, 2014).

According to Bholat (2015), big data can affect economic stability and employment in the long run. For example, the Bank of England (2014) came up with a new strategy of having an *Advanced Analytics Division*, which involved having a special Lab Room. It was operated by a small group of IT experts who manage both structured and unstructured data. The results are disseminated via seminars, intranet, and a data art gallery to update the staff on the usefulness of visualizing data.

Hassani et al. (2018) have broached the issue of Blockchain technology in the banking sector. BlockChain helps the data be more secure, valuable, and structured enough for data analysis, reducing the processing and transaction costs (Fedak, 2018). The various features of BlockChain technology like KYC (Know Your Customer) has helped to prevent money laundering, financing terrorist activities; better transaction speed, i.e., 1000-2000 TPS (Transactions Per Second); improved security- any changes in the data of a block can be monitored to prevent fraud; cost reduction - especially reducing administrative costs while carrying out global inter-bank transactions; smart contracts are made by programming a certain computer code for a financial transaction between two parties, for example, use of smart contracts in travel insurance, etc.

However, BlockChain has its own set of trials, which range from being costly to implement initially; lack of standardization; high energy cost to support BlockChain algorithms; Blockchain deals a lot with Bitcoin crypto-currencies, which many banking intuitions do not want to deal in as currency due to its highly volatile nature; data security has been a concern with BlockChain, etc. (Hassani et al., 2018).

Data mining techniques in the banking sector have helped to enhance the whole banking experience, from improved strategic management to enhanced consumer satisfaction. Data mining techniques like classification, K-means clustering have been used for the following: fraud detection, bad credit scores, investment banking and risk management, consumer profiling, customization, development, segmentation, retention, and acquisition, etc. (Hassani et al., 2018).

The other data mining techniques are Clustered SVM for credit scoring, Decision Support systems for account management, risk management for peer-to-peer lending, and profitability (Hassani et al., 2018).

Benefits of Big Data Analytics in Banking

They are listed as under:

- Has helped to improve services, products, and operations
- It is time for elevation to digital banking from traditional banking using BlockChain, Data mining, and Artificial Intelligence techniques
- Data Mining has been useful for CRM, managing risk, and detecting fraud
- Big data analytics will have a positive effect on financial stability in the long run

(Indriasari et al., 2019; Bholat, 2015)

Conclusion

The results of this review have revealed that most banks use big data analytics for *Fraud Detection* and *Credit risk analysis*. However, the cost of implementation, poor data quality, lack of trained staff, and skeptical banking executives still pose challenges for its uptake in the banking zone. This review has also mentioned the kinds of technologies like BlockChain and Data Mining and their uses in enhancing the whole banking experience in terms of faster transactions at a reduced cost and improvement on customer satisfaction.

References

1. Bedeley, R., Iyer, L., 2014. Big data opportunities and challenges: the case of banking industry, Association for information systems electronic library. Proceedings of the Southern Association for Information Systems Conference, Macon, GA, USA.
2. Bhattacharyya, S., Jha, S., Tharakunnel, K., Westland, J.C., 2011. Data mining for credit card fraud: A comparative study, *Decision Support Systems*, 50(3), 602-613.
3. Bholat, D. (2015). Big Data and Central Banks. *Big Data and Society*, 1-6.
4. Bank of England (2014) Strategic plan: Background information. Available at: <http://www.bankofengland.co.uk/about/Documents/pdfs/stratplanback.pdf>
5. Cavanillas JM, Curry E, Wahlster W, editors. 2016. *New Horizons for a Data-Driven Economy: A Roadmap for Usage and Exploitation of Big Data in Europe*. Springer International Publishing.
6. Coumaros, J., Buvat, J., Auliard, O., Roys, S., Kvj, S., Chretien, L., Clerk, V., 2014. *Big Data Alchemy: How can Banks Maximize the Value of their Customer Data*, Capgemini Group, Retrieved from: https://www.capgemini.com/consulting-se/wp-content/uploads/sites/38/2017/08/big-data-customeranalytics-in-banks_0_0.pdf. (access date: 10/30/2018)
7. Das, P., Verburg, R., Verbraeck, A., & Bonebakker, L. (2018). Barriers to innovation within large financial services firms. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 21(1), 96-112.
8. Davenport, T. H., Harris, J. G., 2007. *Competing on Analytics: The New Science of Winning*, McGraw-Hill Professional, Massachusetts.
9. Fedak, V. (2018). Blockchain and Big Data: the match made in heavens. Available via: <https://towardsdatascience.com/blockchain-and-big-data-the-match-made-in-heavens-337887a0ce73>.
10. Gualtieri, M., 2012. *The pragmatic definition of big data* Retrieved from: https://go.forrester.com/blogs/12-12-05-the_pragmatic_definition_of_big_data.
11. Ghoshal, A., Larson, E.C., Subramanyam, R., Shaw, M.J., 2014. *The impact of business analytics strategy on social, mobile, and cloud computing adoption*, Proceedings of the Thirty Fifth International Conference on Information Systems, Auckland, New Zealand, December 14-17.
12. Sector: Learning for Indian Banks. *Procedia Computer Science*, 50, 643 – 652.
13. Hassani, H., Huang, X., and Silva, E.S. (2018). Banking with blockchain-ed big data. *Journal of Management Analytics*, 5(4). 256-275.
14. Hassani, H., Huang, X., and Silva, E.S. (2018). Digitalization and Big Data Mining in Banking. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, 2, 18.
15. Indriasari, E., Gaol, F.L., and Matsuo, T. (2019). Digital Banking Transformation: Application of Artificial Intelligence and Big Data Analytics for Leveraging Customer Experience in the Indonesia Banking Sector. 8th International Congress on Advanced Applied Informatics (IIAI-AAI). DOI 10.1109/IIAI-AAI.2019.0017
16. He, W., Zhang, W., Tian, X., Tao, R., & Akula, V. (2019). Identifying customer knowledge on social media through data analytics. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*. 32(1), 152-169.

17. Howie, T., 2013. 'The Big Bang: How the Big Data Explosion Is Changing the World', Retrieved from <https://news.microsoft.com/2013/02/11/the-big-bang-how-the-big-data-explosion-is-changing-the-world>.
18. Hoppermann, J., Bennett, M., 2014. 'Big Data In Banking: It's Time To Act', Retrieved from: <https://www.forrester.com/report/Big+Data+In+Banking+Its+Time+To+Act/-/E-RES106842#>
19. Kshetri, N., 2014. 'The emerging role of Big Data in key development issues: opportunities, challenges, and concerns', *Big Data & Society*. 1(2): 1-20
20. Laney, D., 2001. 3D Data management: controlling data volume, velocity, and variety. Retrieved from: <http://blogs.gartner.com/doug-laney/files/2012/01/ad949-3D-Data-Management-Controlling-DataVolume-Velocity-and-Variety.pdf>.
21. Liu, B., 2012. 'Sentiment analysis and opinion mining. Synthesis Lectures on Human Language Technologies', Morgan & Claypool Publishers: 1-167.
22. Manyika, J., Chiu, M., Brown, B., Bughin, J., Dobbs, R., Roxburgh, C., 2011. 'Big data: The next frontier for innovation, competition, and productivity', McKinsey Global Institute
23. Srivastava, U., and Gopalkrishnan, S. (2015). Impact of Big Data Analytics on Banking
24. Wamba, S.F., Akter S., Edwards, A., Chopin, G., Gnanzou, D. 2015. 'How 'big data' can make big impact: findings from a systematic review and a longitudinal case study', *International Journal of Production Economics*, 165:234-246
25. Woerner, S.L., Wixom, B.H., 2015. 'Big data: extending the business strategy toolbox', *Journal of Information Technology*. 30 (1), 60-62